

Parental influence on career choice in Jos North Islamic Secondary Schools, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study sought to analyze parental influences on career choice in Jos North Islamic secondary schools. A sample of ten schools was selected using simple random sampling technique and total of 323 student participated in the research. The data obtained was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result shows that there is positive but non-significant relationship between parental religiosity and career choice of their children. The result also reveals that there is positive and significant relationship between parental socio-cultural and economic influences and their children career choices at 5% and 10% significant level respectively. The study recommends the need to uplift career counseling unit in Islamic secondary schools. It also recommends the development of good relationship between parent and school counsellors towards guiding the students to Islamic career choice preference.

Keywords: Parental Influence; Career Choice; Jos North; Islamic Secondary Schools; Nigeria

1. Introduction

Career is a job or an occupation pursuit for a particular time of persons life. It involves duty or activities to be taken to achieve purpose in both progress as well as opportunities in life. The concept of career can be defined in different context, as for Ohiwerei and Nwosu (2009) they define career as pound of decision and progress that was related to individual role in work knowledge, family and community at large.

Career choice is the most significant aspects of life. Success, happiness and satisfaction of life of an individual depends on the accurate choices of their career. It is unsuitable, inappropriate to be changing career path frequently also it is harmful for personal well-being. According to Okesina and Famolu (2022) apart from being someone's lifestyle, career choice is an important aspect of person's life in the matter of emotional, physical wellbeing and their families. The difficult part of career choice of secondary school students is the type of courses to choose and excel in during enrollment into tertiary institute that will lead them to their career choices and the different influences that follows. Researchers acknowledge that, every time youth are making important choices that are pertinent to their future, how they put their time and effort to the field of study and learning through help in shaping their opportunity throughout their lives. However, their dreams and ambitions do not just pivot their talents alone but, they are influenced by their personal background and families, as well as their knowledge about the world of work. (Mann, et al., 2020)

Career choice in Islam incorporate a lot of consideration which include religious values and ethical morals (Ahmad and Owoyemi, 2012). Ahmad and Owoyemi (2012) also mentioned Islam put special emphasis on work to the extent it considered work as an act of Ibadah itself; in many places in Qur'an and Hadith it was made clear that time should not be wasted. Generally, Muslims have the privilege to choose variety of career as long as they adhere to the Islamic morals and values. On the other hand, it promotes individual and society well-being. Batool and Ghayas (2020) research

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highlighted religious principles as a crucial factor that shaped individual career choice, it has an influence on individual decision making because, it sets some certain thresholds for what was thought to be acceptable within Islamic context. This inferred that individual with vigorous religious orientation may emphasize career that adhere with their religious beliefs and values.

The topic parental influence on career choice of secondary school students have been explored all over the world but specifically, this topic was undertaken in some parts of Nigeria. A similar study recently in 2022 from Kwara State, in 2020 some researchers from Dan Fodio University Sokoto highlight the same topic. Back in 2019 and 2017 research of same topic was conducted in Cross River State and Enugu State respectively. These are few among many considering the diversity of Nigeria with different cultures therefore, this research is undertaken to explore the effect of parental influence on the career choice of Islamic secondary school in Jos North Area of Plateau State.

1.1. Research Objectives

The main aims of the research were specifically to:

- Highlight the extent to which parental religiosity influence the career choice of Islamic Secondary Schools.
- Investigate how does the cultural background of parents influence their children career choice.
- Examine how the economic status of parents affect the career choice of their children.

1.2. Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis guided the research:

- There is no significant relationship between parental religiosity and career choice of Islamic Secondary Schools.
- There is no significant relationship between parents' cultural background and career choice of their children.
- There is no significant relationship between parents' economic status and career choice of their children.

2. Research Methodology

The study employed a quantitative approach. It shows relationships between beliefs, practices and processes in the study. Furthermore, it does not only deal with the attributes of individuals but attributes of the whole sample (Salaria, 2012).

2.1. Sample and Sampling Technique

There are 40 registered Islamic secondary schools in Jos North area of Plateau State and simple random sampling technique was used to select 10 schools from them. Forty Senior Secondary School 2 (SSS2) students were selected from each school making a total of 400 students to response to the questionnaire. Only 323 of the questionnaires were found useful for the analyses.

2.2. Method of Data Collection

The instrument used for the study was a self-design questionnaire. It was made up of two sections; section A consist of the demographic information of the students such as their parent level of adherence to Islamic teachings, income level, and ethnicity. While section B consist of 12 items qualify on four Linkert-type scale of Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD), to obtain responses on parental religiosity, socio-economic background and cultural background affect career choices. The questionnaire was validated by the supervisor of the project and it was administered using online google forms link. The link was shared personally to the schools on phones for the students to answer.

2.3. Method of Data Analysis

Frequencies and percentages were used as descriptive statistics to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents, while the hypotheses proposed were tested using inferential statistics.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Demographic Data of the Respondents

Table 1 indicated that, of the 323 respondents, 62.5 percent are those that have their choices of careers influenced while 37.5 percent of the respondents did not have their career choices influenced. Most of the respondents' age range between 15 to 19.

The table also suggests that parental assistance in the respondents' career choices were grouped into strict, moderate, and partial scaling. The percentage of those that have their parents strictly responding to their career choices is 42.4 while 48.9 percent of the parents were moderate in participating to their child's career choices. Only 8.7 percent received partial responds from their parents on their career choices.

Furthermore, the highest level of education that these parents have was at the degree level. Majority (30%) of them went through secondary school education, as only a few (4.3%) of them stopped at the primary education level, their numbers being close to those that went on to study at tertiary institutions. Of the 323 parents recorded, 38 of them were being grouped as low-class income earners, while 62 were classified as high-class income earners. A huge number of them (69%) were medium-class income earners. They were also classified as either Hausa, Fulani, Yoruba, or Igbo. Most of them (89.5%) are among from the Hausa or Fulani tribe, while only 34 of them are the Yorubas and the Igbos

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents According to their Socioeconomic Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	121	37.5
Female	202	62.5
Career choices		
Yes	202	62.5
No	121	37.5
Age		
15-17	261	80.8
18-21	59	18.3
26-45	3	0.9
Parental assistance		
Partially	28	8.7
Moderately	158	48.9
Strictly	137	42.4
Parent's education		
No formal/Others	44	13.6
Primary/Secondary	104	32.2
Diploma/Degree	175	54.2
Parent's income		
Low	38	11.8
Moderate	223	69.0
High	38	11.8

Parent’s ethnicity		
Hausa/Fulani	289	89.5
Yoruba	28	8.7
Igbo	6	1.9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 Islamic Influence on Career Choices

Statements	SA	A	D	SD
Parents emphasize Islamic values in career choices	133 (41.2)	143 (44.3)	35 (10.8)	12 (3.7)
Parents influence my career aspiration based on Islamic expectation	94 (29.1)	163 (50.5)	56 (17.3)	10 (3.1)
I feel pressure from my parents to choose a career aligned with Islamic values	53 (16.4)	125 (38.7)	120 (37.2)	25 (7.7)
I consider my parent’s Islamic beliefs as a factor in choosing a career.	90 (27.9)	141 (43.7)	74 (22.9)	18 (5.6)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

From table 2, it showed various statements that suggests ways by which parental religiosity influences career choices. Of the 323 respondents, 41.2 percent of them strongly agreed to their parents emphasizing Islamic values in career choices, while 3.7 percent strongly disagreed to this. Based on the statement that parents influence their career aspirations based on Islamic expectation, 29.1 percent strongly agreed while only 3.1 percent of the respondents strongly disagreed. Likewise, 16.4 percent strongly agreed that they were pressured by their parents into choosing a career that aligns with Islamic values, 7.7 percent strongly disagreed. Also, 27.9 percent considered their parents’ Islamic beliefs into choosing their careers while 5.6 percent of them strongly did not.

Table 3 Socio-Cultural Influence on Career Choices

Statements	SA	A	D	SD
I feel pressure from my parent to choose a career that align with their socio-cultural status	44 (13.6)	84 (26.0)	159 (49.2)	36 (11.1)
My parent emphasized the importance of culture in my choice of career	53 (16.4)	117 (36.2)	123 (38.1)	30 (9.3)
My parent disapproved of my choice of career based on cultural values and perspectives	29 (9.0)	102 (31.6)	162 (50.2)	30 (9.3)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Under table 3, it clearly stated how socio-cultural influence affects respondents’ careers choices. 13.6 percent of them feel pressure from their parent to choose a career that align with their socio-cultural status, while 11.1 percent strongly disagreed. There are 16.4 percent of respondents that strongly agreed to the importance of culture and how their parents emphasized its effects in choosing the careers of their children, while 9.3 percent of them strongly disagreed to this. 9.0 percent of respondents strongly agreed to their parents’ disapproval of their career choices based on cultural values and perspectives and 9.3 percent strongly disagreed to this statement.

Table 4 Economic Influence on Career Choices

Statements	SA	A	D	SD
My parent’s income level influenced my choice of career	61 (18.9)	125 (38.7)	119 (36.8)	18 (5.6)
My parent encouraged me to choose my family business than to choose other careers	46 (14.2)	73 (22.6)	151 (46.7)	53 (16.4)
My parent did not approve of my choice of career because of their income level	40 (12.4)	76 (23.5)	175 (54.2)	32 (9.9)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 emphasized ways by which the economy influences the respondents’ choices of their careers. About 19 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to their parents’ income level having influenced the choosing of their careers, while 5.6 percent strongly disagreed. In line with this, there are 14.2 percent of respondents who strongly agreed that they were encouraged by their parents in choosing their family businesses to other careers, while 16.4 percent strongly disagreed. Additionally, 12.4 percent of respondents strongly agreed to their parents’ disapproval of their career choices due to their level of income while 9.9 percent strongly disagreed to this statement.

According to table 5, there is a positive but insignificant relationship between parental Islamic influence and the career choices of their children. This means that Islamic influence of the parents is not a significant determinant of the career choice of Muslim students in the study area. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parental religiosity and career choice of Islamic secondary schools was accepted.

Table 5 Logistic Regression Analysis on Religiosity Influence and Career Choice

Choice Influence	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
Islamic	1.077184	.2197572	0.36	0.716	.722164 1.606735
_cons	1.339416	.823182	0.48	0.634	.4015886 4.467343

In table 6, there is a positive and significant relationship between parental socio-cultural influence and the career choices of their children. This is significant at 5% level. It implies that the socio-cultural influence of the parents has higher probability of influencing the career choices of their children leading to the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between parents’ cultural background and career choice their children.

Table 6 Logistic Regression Analysis on Socio-cultural Influence and Career Choice

Choice Influence	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
Sociocultural	.6843374	.1246121	-2.08	0.037	.4789317 .9778381
_cons	4.296875	2.026153	3.09	0.002	1.705203 10.82752

Table 7 shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between parental economic influence and the career choices of their children. This is significant at 10% level, indicating that the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that the more economically buoyant the parents are, the higher the likelihood that their children’s career choices will be influenced.

Table 7 Logistic Regression Analysis on Economic Influence and Career Choice

Choice Influence	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
Economic	.7159221	.132051	-1.81	0.070	.4987268 1.027706
_cons	3.843805	1.834416	2.82	0.005	1.508461 9.794641

4. Discussion

The finding revealed that, parental Islamic influence is not a strong determinant of career choice of their children in Jos North Area. there is higher probability of parental socio-cultural influence on their children career choice. However, the findings of the current study do not support the previous research of Egbo (2017) which shows that parent support their children to choose a career regardless of their culture. Finally, the response of the student on economic factor shows that it is an important element of career choice. These results agree with the findings of other studies where students from high-income family would rather choose a professional job (Effiom and Peters, 2019). The career choices people made are associated to their social class and their social origins limit the scale of job opportunities (Egbo, 2017).

Conclusion

The study has identified the positive relationship of parental religiosity and student career choice, but it is however not a significant factor to make a career choices of Muslim student in the area of study. It was also gathered from the study that parental socio-cultural and socio-economic status are the important factors influencing career choices of student in Islamic secondary schools.

Recommendations

- There is need to uplift career counseling unit in Islamic Secondary schools.
- There is need to create good relationship between parent and school counselors. It will help the student to be in a proper direction.
- Islamic schools career counselors and Islamic scholars need to establish good inter-personal relationships this will help them guide the student to Islamic career choice preference.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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